

The VECTOBOL initiative: Insect vectors of Bolivia

A very short presentation

F. Lardeux

IRD – UNMR MIVEGEC, Montpellier, France

(pour plus d'informations : frederic.lardeux@ird.fr)

For decades, significant efforts have been made in Bolivia to collect samples and data on insect vectors, which are critical for monitoring vector-borne diseases. Unfortunately, despite these efforts, much of this valuable data and many samples have been lost over time. The information is often not centralized, and there is no long-term scientific memory to preserve this crucial data for research and public health purposes.

In response to this issue, the **VECTOBOL** project was created. This innovative system provides a sustainable solution for the collection, conservation, and management of data on insect vectors in Bolivia. It enables the preservation of ecological and biological data collected in the field, while also supporting the management and long-term conservation of physical samples.

One of the key strengths of **VECTOBOL** lies in its ability to link each sample to detailed information, including species identification (if feasible by the user). This not only preserves the integrity of the samples but also ensures that the associated data is securely stored and remains accessible for future analysis.

Furthermore, **VECTOBOL** plays a critical role in creating a network of scientists and technicians working on insect vectors. This network promotes the exchange of information and best practices among participants, facilitating species identification and knowledge sharing. By bringing together these efforts in a centralized, well-structured database, **VECTOBOL** helps prevent the loss of invaluable information and ensures that these data will remain available for future generations of researchers and public health officials.

VECTOBOL is thus a scientific initiative dedicated to the collection and management of data on insect vectors in Bolivia. The project's primary objective is to establish a comprehensive, centralized database containing essential ecological and biological information for research and the monitoring of vector populations throughout the country.

The project focuses on collecting insect samples from across Bolivia's diverse ecosystems. Each sample is accompanied by basic ecological data, including at least a GPS location and a photograph of the immediate environment where the sample was collected, along with the use of a unique code for each sample. Additionally, more detailed information can be gathered using a standardized form shared among all initiative participants.

VECTOBOL brings together participants from various scientific and technical institutions, such as universities and departmental health services (SEDES), particularly the units responsible for vector control. Each participant manages the data collected by their institution independently while contributing to a centralized database structured through the **REDCap** system. **REDCap**, developed by Vanderbilt University, is a secure data management platform widely used in biomedical research. It allows for precise user management and robust data protection, ensuring that each participating institution retains independence over its data management while contributing to the overall database.

The **VECTOBOL** data is physically centralized on a **Synology NAS** (Network-Attached Storage) located in Montpellier, France, and is managed by the **IRD** (Institut de Recherche pour le Développement). A **Synology NAS** is a network-based storage system that allows centralized storage, secure access, and flexible data management. This infrastructure is ideal for handling large volumes of data, providing optimal security and accessibility. For **VECTOBOL**, the NAS is part of a robust setup with automatic daily backups to three independent servers, ensuring redundancy and maximum protection against data loss.

Access to the full dataset is controlled by the general database administrator, who ensures the fair and transparent management of data usage rights. The exploitation of the data is supervised by this administrator, ensuring coordination among the different stakeholders and respect for data ownership rights.

With **VECTOBOL**, Bolivia is equipped with a vital tool to enhance the monitoring, research, and management of vector-borne diseases, while promoting collaboration among national institutions.